

Effect Of Short Duration Exposure Of Blue Light On Reaction Time And Working Memory Of Young Physically Active Adults Of The Age 18-25 Years: An Experimental Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Reaction time (RT) is utilized in everyday life in various populations for example in athletic training, geriatrics to prevent risk of fall, everyday activities like driving etc. At present, we devote a considerable amount of time to using digital devices for both work and recreation; therefore, it is essential to understand the positive and negative effects of them on the body.

Materials & Methodology: 44 participants satisfying the inclusion criteria were exposed to 30 minutes of short wavelength blue light via short movie played on a laptop screen in a dark room. The reaction time and working memory was assessed pre and post 30 minute of exposure to blue light using computerized tests: Psychomotor vigilance test, Auditory reaction time test and Deary – Liewald task (DLT) for measuring visual, auditory and choice reaction time respectively and N-back test for measuring working memory.

Results: Simple DLT (p value: 0.0459), choice DLT (p value: 0.00057) and N-back test (p value: 0.0153). P value of other tests were insignificant.

Discussion: Results show significant improvements in reaction times and working memory accuracy after a 30-minute exposure. These enhancements are linked to heightened alertness and increased neural activation in prefrontal brain regions. However, visual and auditory reaction times remain unchanged. Further investigation is needed to understand persistence of these effects, highlighting blue light's promising role in potential cognitive enhancement and physiotherapeutic interventions.

Conclusion: The results suggest that short duration blue light exposure during the day affects choice reaction time and working memory positively.

Keywords: blue light, reaction time, screen time, working memory

INTRODUCTION

Reaction time is defined as the time lapse between the onset of a stimulus and the initiation of a movement response. Reaction time (RT) is a reliable indicator of the speed of processing of sensory stimulus by central nervous system and its execution in the form of motor response.^[1] Reaction time serves an

important function in day to day activities (e.g. driving) and many recreational activities like athletics, football, basketball, cricket, etc. Reaction time is composed of three components. The first is perception time, referring to the duration needed to sense and recognize the stimulus. The second component, decision time, denotes the period required to choose a suitable response.

The final component is motor time, which reflects the time taken to carry out the response following the command.

Working memory is a multicomponent system that manipulates information storage for greater and more complex cognitive utility. It has often been connected or related to intelligence, information processing, executive function, comprehension, problem-solving, and learning.^[2] Working memory is an active and fairly instant process. It allows us to use new and learned information while we are in the middle of an activity.

Attention ensures the selection of basic elements (or pieces of information); working memory ensures that the selected elements are maintained active during processing and assembled.^[3]

Blue light plays a key role in regulating the circadian rhythm by influencing melatonin secretion. In low or absent blue-light conditions, melatonin levels rise and promote sleep, while exposure to blue light suppresses melatonin production, thereby enhancing alertness and delaying sleep onset.^[4] In earlier times, artificial lighting was minimal, so people spent their nights in natural darkness, which helped regulate and maintain a healthy sleep-wake cycle in harmony with the body's biological rhythms.^[4]

In today's fast-paced, digitally driven world, reliance on gadgets such as mobile phones, laptops, and computers has increased substantially for everyday activities, especially among the younger population... People are now being exposed to more of the blue light that these devices' screens produce, which has both visual and non-visual effects. These devices having LED screen emit short wavelength high energy blue light i.e. within 450-485nm range, which on exposure have shown to alter melatonin production, circadian rhythm regulation, sleep propensity, mood, and alertness.^[5]

The daytime alerting effects of blue light are believed to be mediated by melanopsin-expressing intrinsically photosensitive retinal ganglion cells, which project beyond the hypothalamus to multiple brain regions.^[6] Among these pathways, indirect activation of the locus coeruleus results in widespread cortical release of norepinephrine, thereby

promoting increased arousal and alertness.^[7]^[8]

Neurocomputational frameworks propose that decision-making operations, including those dependent on working memory, involve an inherent balance between response speed and accuracy. Accordingly, exposure to blue light may be expected to reduce response latency in such tasks by elevating baseline neural activation. Evidences shows both the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and ventrolateral prefrontal cortex are critically involved in the encoding, retention, and retrieval of information during working memory tasks. Alkozei et al in 2016 in his study, suggested that a single, relatively short exposure to blue wavelength light of only 30 minutes can increase neural activation over the subsequent 40-minute period within those prefrontal areas most critical for successful working memory performance. Smith R., Pisner D et al's work has shown that even short bursts of blue light for periods lasting from 50 seconds to 20 minutes are effective at activating similar regions of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and ventrolateral prefrontal cortex during auditory working memory tasks.

The prolonged effect i.e. till 40 minutes post exposure may be a result of sustained noradrenergic activation^[9] Prolonged exposure to artificial blue light has been shown to disrupt sleep patterns and adversely affect cognitive functioning. Cognitive performance encompasses domains such as memory, mood, attention, alertness, and regulation of the sleep-wake cycle. Conversely, exposure to short-wavelength bright light suppresses melatonin secretion and enhances alertness.^[10]

Reaction time is widely applied in daily life across diverse populations, including athletic training and geriatric care for fall-risk prevention, as well as routine activities such as driving. In the modern era, substantial time is spent using digital devices for occupational and recreational purposes, making it important to understand both their beneficial and adverse effects on the human body. Literature is available on effects of short duration blue light exposure in the night time have and has shown to alter the reaction time and working memory of the participants.

There is paucity of research on daytime exposure of the blue light hence the goal of this study is to identify any changes in reaction time and working memory post exposure during daytime. From a physiotherapy perspective, an important area for future research lies in determining whether these effects can be therapeutically applied in clinical practice for conditions known to impair reaction time, such as Parkinson's disease, or whether they should be mitigated through public education regarding their potential adverse effects, based on the findings of the present study.

OBJECTIVES

- To expose the individuals in age group 18-25 years involved in moderate physical activity to 30 minutes of blue light via short movie in a dark room.
- To assess reaction time and working memory pre and post 30 minute of exposure to blue light using computerized tests: Psychomotor vigilance test, Auditory reaction time test and Deary – Liewald task for measuring reaction time and N-back test for measuring working memory in 18-25 year individuals with moderate physical activity.
- To compare and study effects on reaction time and working memory

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Alkozei A, Smith R, Pisner DA, Vanuk JR, Berryhill SM, Fridman A, Shane BR, Knight SA, Killgore WD.** Exposure to blue light has been shown to enhance functional activation of the prefrontal cortex during working memory performance. In a study involving 35 healthy participants (18 females), individuals were exposed to either blue or amber wavelength light for 30 minutes in a darkened environment, followed immediately by functional magnetic resonance imaging while performing an N-back working memory task. Participants in the blue light condition demonstrated faster response times and greater activation in both the dorsolateral and ventrolateral prefrontal cortices compared to those

exposed to amber control light. Moreover, increased activation of the ventrolateral prefrontal cortex was positively associated with faster N-back task responses. Consistent with these findings, previous studies have reported that brief exposures to blue light, ranging from 50 seconds to 20 minutes, are sufficient to elicit activation of similar dorsolateral and ventrolateral prefrontal regions during auditory working memory tasks.

2. **Bansal N, Prakash NR, Randhawa JS, Kalra P.** Effects of blue light on cognitive performance. *Int Res J Eng Technol.* 2017;4(6):2434-42. ^[11] 7 participants were called one by one each day to perform some series of tasks on LED screen interface. After the first part of study was done same participants were recalled to perform same tasks on blue light filter interface. Room was setup in such a way that only the light from the laptop should fall onto participant eyes. HP laptop was used as a user interface. On the other hand for second screen interface, Eye safe blue light filter with RPF-30 was applied on the HP laptop as which claims to block about 30% of blue light. The total study duration was five hours, encompassing EEG electrode placement and a dark adaptation period, followed by 3.5 hours of bright screen exposure. Verbal memory performance showed a gradual decline across both screen conditions; however, participants using the blue light-filtered screen consistently demonstrated higher scores compared to those exposed to the standard LED screen. In terms of sustained attention, reaction times increased significantly among participants exposed to the blue light-filtered screen.
3. **Vandewalle G, Baeteu E, Phillips C, Degueldre C, Moreau V, Sterpenich V, Albouy G, Darsaud A, Desseilles M, Dang-Vu TT, Peigneux P.** Daytime light exposure dynamically enhances brain responses. *Current Biology.* 2006 Aug 22;16:1616-21 ^[10]. 19 subjects were scanned during six consecutive 8 min sessions during which they performed an

auditory oddball task. Data were acquired before, during and after one eye was exposed for 21 min to a bright white light. The same protocol was followed on another day, but no light was administered. The order of the day with and without light was counterbalanced over subjects. Light-induced improvement in subjective alertness was linearly related to responses in the posterior thalamus. In addition, light enhanced responses in a set of cortical areas supporting attentional oddball effects, and it prevented decreases of activity otherwise observed during continuous darkness. Responses to light were remarkably dynamic. They declined within minutes after the end of the light stimulus, following various region-specific time courses. These findings suggest that light can modulate activity of subcortical structures involved in alertness, thereby dynamically promoting cortical activity in networks involved in ongoing nonvisual cognitive processes.

4. **Silvani MI, Werder R, Perret C.** The influence of blue light on sleep, performance and wellbeing in young adults: A systematic review. *Frontiers in physiology*. 2022 Aug 16;13:943108 ^[12] Randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies, and cross-sectional studies published in English were included in this review. Eligible studies examined the effects of blue light exposure on sleep, performance, wellbeing, or combinations of these outcomes. The findings of this systematic review suggest that blue light exposure may influence sleep, performance, and overall wellbeing. Most studies reported beneficial effects, including enhanced cognitive performance, increased alertness, and reduced reaction times. Improvements in cognitive functioning are particularly relevant for sports requiring teamwork and rapid decision-making. Furthermore, heightened alertness may contribute to injury prevention, while improved wellbeing could reduce stress and subsequently lower risk.

Conversely, a notable adverse effect associated with blue light exposure is the potential reduction in sleep quality and duration, which may negatively affect performance and recovery. Overall, the specific effects of blue light exposure remain incompletely understood, highlighting the need for further investigation before drawing definitive, evidence-based conclusions. Based on the current evidence, additional research is warranted to determine whether blue light exposure can enhance specific aspects of athletic performance through its effects on sleep, performance, and wellbeing.

5. **Oh JH, Yoo H, Park HK, Do YR.** Analysis of circadian properties and healthy levels of blue light from smartphones at night. *Scientific reports*. 2015 Jun 18;5(1):11325 ^[13]. This study proposes representative figures of merit to evaluate circadian and visual performance for the safe and efficient use of smartphone displays. Recently developed metrics, including circadian luminous efficacy of radiation (CER) and circadian illuminance (CIL), which are closely associated with human circadian regulation and health, were employed to compare three commercially available smartphone display technologies. In addition, both nonvisual and visual optical characteristics of the displays were assessed under varying screen-eye distances and controlled brightness levels.

The findings indicate that the human circadian system is most responsive to near-monochromatic blue light in the wavelength range of approximately 450–470 nm. Blue light emitted from all tested smartphone displays, including LED-backlit liquid crystal displays (LCDs) and active-matrix organic light-emitting diode (AMOLED) displays, was found to suppress melatonin secretion. As melatonin regulation plays a critical role in maintaining circadian rhythm and overall health, this suppression has important physiological implications. Spectral analysis revealed that all displays exhibited a

pronounced, narrow-band blue emission peak, regardless of display technology, reflecting the wide color gamut design of modern screens.

Moreover, smartphone use in brightly lit environments, compared with dark conditions, was shown to exert a greater disruptive effect on the natural melatonin secretion-suppression cycle, leading to significantly reduced nocturnal melatonin levels and potential adverse health consequences. Importantly, the results suggest that reducing the brightness setting alone is insufficient to mitigate melatonin suppression when using an LCD smartphone in a bright environment during activities such as typing or reading.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Study Design: Experimental research design

Study Setting: Clinical

Study Population: Active individuals i.e. individuals performing moderate intensity activities / playing sports 3-5 times a week and are in the age group 18-25 years.

Sample Size: 44

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Exposed to LED devices for at least 3 hours per day
2. Using at least one of these devices on a day to day basis for the past 2-3 years
3. No comorbidities
4. Optimum hand function
5. Absence of hearing issues
6. 150 minutes of vigorous intensity activity or 300 minutes of moderate intensity activity per week
7. Minimum of 2 sessions of muscle strengthening activity per week

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Intake of caffeine or any other stimulants or psychoactive drugs 12 hours prior to the test
2. Sleep less than 6-7 hours,
3. Exposure to any LED device for more than 2-3 hours in the past 6 hours
4. Any sort of vigorous physical activity prior to the test

5. Visually impaired individuals like color blindness and diminished pupils

Procedure:

The study was conducted in a single sitting using an experimental pre-post design. Participants aged 18–25 years who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled. All participants were exposed to shortwavelength blue light for 30 minutes during daytime (2:00 PM to 3:00 PM). The exposure was administered via a short movie displayed on a 14-inch laptop screen in a darkened room with ambient illumination maintained between 150–300 lux. A fixed viewing distance of 1.5 feet between the laptop screen and the participants' eyes was maintained throughout the exposure period.

Prior to the intervention, basic demographic details were recorded, followed by a pre-exposure assessment that included measurements of visual reaction time, auditory reaction time, choice reaction time, and working memory. These assessments were conducted using the same laptop screen, which also served as the source of blue light exposure.

Immediately after completion of the 30-minute exposure, a post-exposure assessment was carried out using the same outcome measures as those employed during the pre-exposure phase.

A separate control group was not included, as the study employed a single-group experimental pretest-posttest design, wherein each participant served as their own control. This design was selected to evaluate the acute effects of short-wavelength blue light exposure on reaction time and working memory within the same individuals.

Pre and Post Exposure Assessment:

1. **Visual Reaction Time:** Psychomotor vigilance test – Subject were asked to single click on the box as soon as possible after red numbers appear in the box. The red numbers will appear at random times. The test lasted for 2 minutes. When the test is carried out for entire 2 minutes it gives us accurate assessment. Those response

- time less than 100 msec known as false start wear excluded from final analysis.
- Auditory Reaction Time:** The participant was given a preview of the auditory stimulus. They were asked to click or press spacebar as soon as they hear the stimulus. The test was carried out for 2 minutes and average score was taken.
 - Choice Reaction Time:** Deary-Liewald RT task - In the Simple Reaction Time (SRT) task, subjects responded to a single stimulus by pressing a designated button or key. In the Choice Reaction Time (CRT) task, four different stimuli were presented, and subjects were required to select and press the button corresponding to the appropriate response. The SRT protocol

included 8 practice trials followed by 20 test trials, whereas the CRT protocol comprised 8 practice trials and 40 test trials.

- N-Back Test:** The subject were presented with a continuous sequence of stimuli and were required to identify instances in which the current stimulus matched the stimulus presented n positions earlier in the sequence.

RESULTS

Data was collected and analysed using GraphPad Prism 10.2.1. Analysis was done by using paired T test for data which passed normality tests and Wilcoxon paired test for data which did not pass normality tests.

Table 1: Gender distribution of study participants

Gender	n
Male	23
Female	21
Total	44

Graph 1: Out of the 44 participants, 23 were males i.e. 52.27% and 21 were females i.e. 47.72%

Table 2: Auditory reaction time test

Auditory Reaction Time	Mean Values
Pre	411 ms
Post	398ms

Graph 2: As depicted in the bar graph above, the pre test reaction time mean was 411 ms and post-test mean was 398 ms giving a mean difference of 13 ms. This shows that there was an decrease in the auditory reaction time post exposure of blue light.

Table 3: Simple and Choice reaction time by the Deary Liewald Task

	Simple Reaction	Choice Reaction
Pre	334	459
Post	324	440

Graph 3: The above graph depicts the pre and post simple and choice reaction times taken by the Deary Liewald Task. As seen in the graph there was a decrease in both the simple and choice reaction times post exposure.

Table 4: Working memory test - N batch test

Working memory	Pre	Post
N batch test	64.3%	73.3%

Graph 4: The variable chosen for comparing pre and post N back test values was the percentage of correct matches during the test. According to the data, the percentage of correct answers increased by 9% after exposure of blue light.

The data which passed normality test was analyzed using paired T test i.e. Psychomotor Vigilance test, Choice reaction time and N-back test. The data which did not pass normality test was analyzed using Wilcoxon test. The analysis results were as follows.

Table 5: Pre & Post assessment variables

Test	Pre assessment Mean \pm SD	Post assessment Mean \pm SD	P value
Psychomotor Vigilance Test	408 \pm 50.7	405 \pm 55.6	0.5965
Auditory Reaction Time Test	411 \pm 83.7	398 \pm 44.5	0.4094
Simple DLT	334 \pm 51.9	324 \pm 67.9	0.0459 *
Choice DLT	458 \pm 71.4	440 \pm 62.3	0.00057 *
N-back test	64.2 \pm 20.6%	73.2 \pm 21.1%	0.0153 *

Significant P value - * , SD – Standard Deviation , DLT – Deary Liewald Task

DISCUSSION

The main objective of the present study was to thoroughly examine the impact of short-duration exposure to blue light during the daytime on the reaction time and working memory functions of young, physically active individuals.

According to the detailed data analysis conducted, notable findings emerged indicating that following a 30-minute period of exposure to blue light, a significant reduction was observed in both simple and choice reaction times in the Deary – Liewald task (DLT), alongside an evident improvement in the accuracy of responses in the N-back test. From the result of the current study it was found that 75% of individuals showed a decrease in their choice reaction times in the Deary – Liewald task after the exposure to blue light for 30 minutes indicating quicker brain processing due to the alerting effects of blue light.

The enhancement of daytime alertness associated with blue light exposure is likely mediated by the indirect activation of melanopsin-expressing retinal ganglion cells on the locus coeruleus, leading to widespread cortical release of norepinephrine and increased arousal.^[8] This elevation in alertness may explain the observed reductions in both simple and choice reaction times following blue light stimulation.^[9]

Interestingly when compared to the physiology of choice reaction time, while evaluating the effect on visual and auditory reaction times, it was noted that these responses do not primarily necessitate engagement of the prefrontal cortex for processing. Even though there was surge in alertness levels, there were no significant alterations detected in the visual and auditory reaction times.

Although not tested in the current study, it is possible that these effects can persist for a certain duration even after the removal of blue light exposure. This persistence of effects is what would be desirable to enable this method to be used in rehabilitation. However, as this

prolonged effect is still unclear it becomes an open question to further research.

As for the results of the working memory task, out of 44 individuals 63.6% i.e 28 individuals showed an increase in percentage of correct answers which is consistent with insights derived from prior studies which propose that a brief exposure of just 30 minutes to blue light of a specific wavelength has the capacity to enhance neural activation within the crucial dorsal and ventral prefrontal brain regions which are essential for successful working memory execution.^[9] This phenomenon could plausibly account for the observed enhancement in the participants' performance during the N-back test, showcasing the positive impact of blue light exposure on cognitive functions.

This study does not delve into the long term effects and the persistence of the effects post the exposure of blue light, a previous study shows that brain activation and improved working memory task performance as a result of light exposure can substantially endure well beyond the exposure period and adds to emerging work suggesting that prolonged blue light exposure (30 minutes or more) may continue to affect brain function even after termination of the light.^[14] This broadens the spectrum of possibility to utilizing blue light as a treatment in rehabilitation. This potential role of blue light in rehabilitation is indeed an intriguing possibility which should be investigated further for the future benefit of physiotherapeutic treatment.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, together with findings from previous studies and the present findings, the results suggest that short duration blue light exposure during the day affects choice reaction time and working memory positively.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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